

From the Edge

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Abstract. *From the Edge* is one of a series of audiovisual installations that explores nonlinear audiovisual installations in a process I have come to term as *Ecological Performativity*. These works explore the relationships of environment, material, and process, and are derived from an intensive data-gathering procedure and immersion within the respective environments.

1. Artwork Proposal

Figure 1. St. John's SmartBay Buoy

From the Edge is one of a series of audiovisual installations by the author that explores the environment of East Coast Newfoundland. The work expands on my use of

environmental datasets as an artistic device to create nonlinear artworks for public engagement. The creative system is coded to live-stream data off the SmartAtlantic St. John's Buoy, which is located 1 kilometre offshore of Cape Spear, NL (Fig. 1). The buoy is capable of measuring and transmitting a variety of atmospheric and surface conditions including: surface temperature; wind speed and direction; wave height, period and direction; as well as current speed and direction. From the Edge is coded to stream and parse these data-sets to trigger and shift parameters of this nonlinear work, which includes a visual particle system, audio and visual field recording material captured off this coast, a live streaming hydrophone feed from the St. John's SmartBay Buoy and improvised musical motifs. Developed in Max/MSP, the work continually evolves depending on the transmitted measurements.

Figure 2. *From the Edge* particle system generated from Ocean datasets streamed off the SmartBay St. John's buoy, NL, Canada.

Figure 3. From the Edge data-streaming code

2. Technical and logistical requirements

From the Edge can be live-streamed from my location in Montreal and onto a twitch account. From there, anyone can view the work via the following twitch account link.